

EXPEDITION REPORT

Expedition dates:
05 – 18 July 2025

Report published: May 2026

**Love / hate relationships: Monitoring
the return of the wolf to the German
state of Lower Saxony**

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Authors:

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ABSTRACT

Background and introduction

The return of the Eurasian wolf *Canis lupus lupus* to the German state of Lower Saxony represents a significant ecological development that necessitates active monitoring to mitigate human-wildlife conflict and understand population dynamics. By the end of the 2024/2025 monitoring year, Germany recorded 219 confirmed wolf packs, 43 pairs and 14 single resident wolves. Lower Saxony itself hosted 54 packs prior to the July 2025 expedition, a number that increased to 59 packs by October 2025, indicating that the region continues to offer suitable, unoccupied habitats. This report details the active monitoring fieldwork conducted by Biosphere Expeditions in collaboration with the state environmental authority, NLWKN (Niedersächsischer Landesbetrieb für Wasserwirtschaft, Küsten- und Naturschutz) and local wolf commissioners.

Objectives

The primary objective of the 2025 expedition was the collection of non-invasive samples (scats and tracks) to elucidate wolf ecology, pack numbers, movement patterns, and dietary habits. The project sought to provide robust, high-quality data to support the state's official monitoring programme and to foster public acceptance of wildlife research through citizen science.

Methodology and team composition

Fieldwork was conducted between 5 July and 18 July 2025, involving two groups of national and international citizen scientists totalling 19 participants. Operating from a base at NaturCampus Bockum, the teams covered 26 individual 10 km x 10 km grid cells of the European Environment Agency (EEA) reference system. Surveying was performed on foot, exclusively along forest paths and forestry roads, covering a cumulative distance of approximately 650 km.

Results

The expedition successfully collected 79 scat samples for inclusion in the official monitoring database. According to the SCALP classification system, 11% (n=9) of samples were categorised as C1 hard evidence, 18% (n=14) as C2 confirmed observations and 66% (n=52) as C3/C3a unconfirmed observations. Four samples (5 %) were assigned to other species. Genetic analysis of 13 fresh samples confirmed nine to be of wolf origin, with three samples assigned to specific individuals, including a female born in 2024. Dietary analysis of 121 samples from previous expeditions (2022–2023) indicated that wolves primarily consume wild ungulates: roe deer *Capreolus capreolus* was detected in 75% of samples, red deer *Cervus elaphus* in 35%, and wild boar *Sus scrofa* in 13%. Livestock consumption was notably low, appearing in fewer than 5% of samples.

Conclusion

The 2025 expedition contributed 45% of all scat samples (C1, C2, and C3) assessed by the state's official programme during the third quarter of the year. Over the period of 2017–2025, expeditions have provided an average of 66.5% of all C1 hard evidence scat samples collected annually in Lower Saxony. These results highlight the critical role of citizen science in wildlife conservation, providing a cost-effective and scientifically rigorous method for monitoring expanding predator populations.

ZUSAMMENFASSUNG

Hintergrund und Einleitung

Die Rückkehr des Wolfes *Canis lupus lupus* in das Bundesland Niedersachsen stellt eine bedeutende ökologische Entwicklung dar, die ein aktives Monitoring erfordert, um Mensch-Wildtier-Konflikte zu minimieren und die Populationsdynamik zu verstehen. Bis zum Ende des Monitoringjahres 2024/2025 wurden in Deutschland 219 bestätigte Wolfsrudel, 43 Paare und 14 sesshafte Einzelwölfe registriert. In Niedersachsen selbst stieg die Zahl der Rudel von 54 vor der Expedition im Juli 2025 auf 59 im Oktober 2025 an. Dies verdeutlicht, dass die Region weiterhin geeignete, unbesetzte Habitate bietet. Dieser Bericht dokumentiert die aktive Feldarbeit im Rahmen des Monitorings, die von Biosphere Expeditions in Zusammenarbeit mit dem Niedersächsischen Landesbetrieb für Wasserwirtschaft, Küsten- und Naturschutz (NLWKN) sowie lokalen Wolfsberatern durchgeführt wurde.

Ziele

Das primäre Ziel der Expedition 2025 war die Sammlung nicht-invasiver Proben (Losungen und Spuren), um Erkenntnisse über die Ökologie der Wölfe, die Anzahl der Rudel, Bewegungsmuster und Ernährungsgewohnheiten zu gewinnen. Das Projekt zielte darauf ab, belastbare und qualitativ hochwertige Daten für das offizielle Monitoringprogramm des Landes bereitzustellen und gleichzeitig durch Citizen Science (Bürgerwissenschaft) die öffentliche Akzeptanz der Wildtierforschung zu fördern.

Methodik und Teambzusammensetzung

Die Geländearbeit fand zwischen dem 5. und 18. Juli 2025 statt. Beteiligt waren zwei Gruppen aus nationalen und internationalen Bürgerwissenschaftlern und -innen mit insgesamt 19 Teilnehmenden. Vom Stützpunkt im NaturCampus Bockum aus deckten die Teams 26 einzelne Rasterzellen (10 km x 10 km) des Referenzsystems der Europäischen Umweltagentur (EUA) ab. Die Kartierung erfolgte zu Fuß, ausschließlich auf Wald- und Forstwegen, wobei eine Gesamtstrecke von etwa 650 km zurückgelegt wurde.

Ergebnisse

Im Rahmen der Expedition konnten 79 Losungsproben für die offizielle Monitoring-Datenbank gesammelt werden. Gemäß den SCALP-Kriterien wurden 11% (n=9) der Proben als C1 (eindeutiger Nachweis), 18% (n=14) als C2 (bestätigter Hinweis) und 66% (n=52) als C3/C3a (unbestätigter Hinweis) eingestuft. Lediglich vier Proben (5%) wurden einer anderen Tierart zugeordnet. Genetische Analysen von 13 frischen Proben bestätigten bei neun Proben die Herkunft vom Wolf, wobei drei Proben spezifischen Individuen zugeordnet werden konnten, darunter eine im Jahr 2024 geborene Fähe. Die Nahrungsanalysen von 121 Proben früherer Expeditionen (2022–2023) zeigten, dass sich die Wölfe hauptsächlich von wilden Huftieren ernähren: Rehwild *Capreolus capreolus* wurde in 75% der Proben nachgewiesen, Rotwild *Cervus elaphus* in 35% und Schwarzwild *Sus scrofa* in 13%. Der Anteil von Nutztieren war mit unter 5% der Proben auffallend gering.

Fazit

Die Expedition von 2025 lieferte 45% aller im dritten Quartal des Jahres für das offizielle Landesprogramm bewerteten Losungsproben (C1, C2 und C3). Im Zeitraum von 2017 bis 2025 stellten diese Expeditionen durchschnittlich 66,5% aller jährlich in Niedersachsen gesammelten C1-Nachweise durch Losungen bereit. Diese Ergebnisse unterstreichen die bedeutende Rolle von Bürgerwissenschaft für den Naturschutz, da sie eine kosteneffiziente und wissenschaftlich fundierte Methode zur Überwachung expandierender Raubtierpopulationen darstellt.

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1. Expedition review

M. Hammer (editor)
Biosphere Expeditions

1.1. Background & research area

Background information, location conditions and the research area are as per [Schütte & Hammer \(2018\)](#), [Schütte & Hammer \(2019\)](#), [Schütte et al. \(2020\)](#) and [Schütte et al. \(2023\)](#).

The aim of the expedition was to actively monitor for wolf *Canis lupus lupus* signs such as scats and tracks so that wolf ecology and population dynamics (wolf and pack numbers, group sizes, movements, diet) can be elucidated to mitigate human-wolf conflict.

For the 2023 expedition, the expedition base changed to [NaturCampus Bockum](#) which was again the base of the expedition in 2025. The base has proven to be a perfect starting point for the monitoring activities and an ideal accommodation for the expedition participants.

1.2. Dates & team

In 2025 expedition ran over a period of two weeks divided into two 7-day groups, each composed of a team of national and international citizen scientists, a scientist and another helper as well as an expedition leader. Group dates were as shown in the team list below.

The expedition team was recruited by Biosphere Expeditions and consisted of a mixture of ages, nationalities and backgrounds. They were (in alphabetical order and with country of residence):

5-11 July 2025: Sharon Amos (UK), Maria Aragon (Spain), Neil Goodall (UK), John Hogan (USA), Corinna Kuhn-Seele (Germany), Silke Kutzer (Germany), Jana Lippmann (Germany), Karin Schneeberger (Switzerland, press, [see coverage](#)), Josefine Vater (Germany).

12-18 July 2025: Jenan Anwar Alasfoor (Oman), Michail Davies (UK), Stefanie Düsterhus (Germany), Christiane Flechtner (Germany, press, see coverage in [FAZ](#) and [TOP Magazin](#)), Jacqueline Goerck (Brazil), Neil Goodall (UK), Ben Rees (UK), Niki Rouse (Australia), Claudia Schank (Germany), Anne Schroedter (Germany).

In addition for some or all of the time: Charlotte Steinberg (expedition scientist), Beate Stahmer (helper) and Malika Fettak (expedition leader) as well as wolf commissioners Peter Schütte and Kenny Kenner.

A medical umbrella, safety and evacuation procedures were in place, but did not have to be invoked as there were no medical incidents.

1.3. Partners

Biosphere Expeditions' main partner on this expedition was the state's environmental authority the [NLWKN](#) (Niedersächsischer Landesbetrieb für Wasserwirtschaft, Küsten- und Naturschutz, = Lower Saxony Water Management, Coastal Defence and Nature Conservation Agency), which is officially responsible for the monitoring of all wildlife in the state. The authority's [Wolfsbüro](#) (wolf bureau) staff were closely involved in all expedition activities. Other partners included the [Landesforsten](#) (state forestry department), district and communal authorities, [BIO-Hotel Kenners LandLust](#), [Wolfcenter Dörverden](#) and [NaturCampus Bockum](#). Local people such as hunters and foresters supported the expedition by giving information about (possible) wolf presence on the spot. Furthermore, the expedition includes regular exchanges with the state hunting association.

1.4. Further information & enquiries

More background information on Biosphere Expeditions in general and on this expedition in particular including pictures, diary excerpts and a copy of this report can be found on the Biosphere Expeditions website www.biosphere-expeditions.org.

Project updates, reports and publications:

<https://www.researchgate.net/lab/Biosphere-Expeditions-Matthias-Hammer>

Diary for this expedition:

<https://blog.biosphere-expeditions.org/category/expedition-blogs/germany-2025/>

Media Release of this expedition:

[Citizen scientists make significant contribution to wolf monitoring in Lower Saxony \(Germany\) as hunting debate intensifies](#)

Expedition details, background, pictures, videos, etc.:

<https://www.biosphere-expeditions.org/germany>

1.5. Acknowledgements

We would like to thank all the expedition citizen scientists, who not only dedicated their spare time to helping but also, through their expedition contributions, funded the research. Thank you also to those who brought their own cars and supported the expedition in this way too. Thank you to all our partners mentioned above, especially those at the 'Wolfsbüro' at NLWKN and to all those professionals who provided assistance and information. Special thanks also go to the local 'wolf commissioner' (Wolfsberater) Kenny Kenner and helpers working on a voluntary basis in support of the expedition. Their efforts and local knowledge were crucial to the success of our field work. Thanks also to the state forestry department (Niedersächsische Landesforsten) for their co-operation. Finally, thank you to the staff at NaturCampus Bockum, led by Dr. Susanne Eich, for being such excellent hosts and making us feel at home, and to anonymous reviewers for helpful comments on the manuscript.

1.6. Expedition budget

Each citizen scientist paid a contribution of €2,390 per person per seven-day period towards expedition costs. The contribution covered accommodation and meals, supervision and induction, special research equipment and all transport from and to the team assembly point. It did not cover excess luggage charges, travel insurance, personal expenses such as telephone bills, souvenirs etc., or visa and other travel expenses to and from the assembly point (e.g. international flights). Details on how this contribution was spent are given below.

Income	€
Expedition contributions	39,970
Expenditure	
Expedition base includes all food & services	9,440
Transport includes hire cars, fuel, taxis in Germany	1,238
Equipment and hardware includes research materials & gear etc. purchased internationally & locally	159
Staff includes local and Biosphere Expeditions staff salaries and travel expenses	8,509
Administration includes miscellaneous fees & sundries	1,397
Team recruitment Germany as estimated % of annual PR costs for Biosphere Expeditions	8,998
Income – Expenditure	10,228
Total percentage spent directly on project	74%

2. Monitoring wolves in Lower Saxony

Charlotte Steinberg
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Peter Schütte
Wolf Commissioner, Lower Saxony

2.1. Introduction

The expedition's rationale, background, materials and methods, and training of citizen scientists are described in [Schütte & Hammer \(2018\)](#), [Schütte & Hammer \(2019\)](#), [Schütte et al. \(2020\)](#) and [Schütte et al. \(2023\)](#).

Wolf territories and population dynamics in Germany and Lower Saxony in 2024/2025

At the end of the monitoring year 2024/2025 (01 May 2024 - 30 April 2025) there were 219 confirmed wolf packs, 43 wolf pairs and 14 single resident wolves in Germany. The area of occurrence has increased by just under 5% compared to the previous monitoring year and has therefore also not changed significantly. The populations in the main distribution area in the east and north of the country have continued to become denser, while in the south and southwest of Germany there have been few changes – in some cases even decreases in areas. Wolf packs were confirmed in twelve federal states during the monitoring year 2024/25, most of them in Brandenburg (54), Lower Saxony (54), Saxony (35), Saxony-Anhalt (31) and Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania (28) (DBBW 2025) (Figs. 2.1a & 2.1b). In the federal state of Lower Saxony, prior to the 2025 expedition commencing, the numbers of wolves were 54 wolf packs, six wolf pairs and two single wolves (LJN 2025a). In October 2025, after the expedition, numbers increased to 59 wolf packs, three wolf pairs and two single wolves. This development (Table 2.1) illustrates that Lower Saxony still offers suitable habitats, which are not fully occupied by wolves.

Table 2.1. Wolf population dynamics in Lower Saxony January 2025 – October 2025.

Time	Wolf packs	Wolf pairs	Single wolves
Jan – Mar 2025	54	6	2
Jul – Sep 2025	59	3	2

Study site and 2025 focus areas

Focus areas of the 2025 expedition are shown in Figure 2.1e (CORINE) and 2.1f (Google).

Focus areas were chosen in collaboration with local people (such as wolf commissioners, foresters, hunters) and authorities, such as the 'Wolfsbüro' at [NLWKN](#) (the wolf bureau at the state environment department). Such collaborations, especially with the wolf commissioners and the wolf bureau, are critical to the project's success. An additional and welcome side effect is that acceptance for the project, as well as citizen science projects in general and in the field of wildlife monitoring and research, are fostered.

Figure 2.1a.

Wolf territories in Germany on 30 April 2025 (DBBW 2026a).

Rudel (blue) = wolf pack

Paar (red) = wolf pair

Einzeltier (yellow) = single individual

The text reads “219 packs, 43 pairs, 14 territorial individuals are known, as well as 770 juveniles (41 packs crossing state boundaries).

Figure 2.1b. Distribution of wolves in Germany in 2024/2025 on the EEA grid system (DBBW 2026b).
 Green cell = wolf presence confirmed in accordance with monitoring standards.
 Green cell with black dot = wolf presence and reproduction confirmed.

Figure 2.1c.

Wolf territories in Lower Saxony after the third quarter 2025 (LJN 2025c)

The reference reads:

Wolfsrudel (green) = wolf pack

Wolfsrudel (Nachweis ausstehend)* (shaded green) = wolf pack (to be confirmed)*

Wolfspaar (orange) = wolf pair

Residenter Einzelwolf (blue) = resident individual

Unklar (grey) = unclear

Unter Beobachtung (white) = under observation

*To be confirmed = pack existence through evidence of reproduction or more than two pack members has not yet been confirmed in the current monitoring season.

Figure 2.1d.

Distribution of wolves in Lower Saxony in the monitoring year 2024/2025 on the EEA grid system (LJN 2026a).

The reference reads:

1 piece of C1 hard evidence (light blue)

2-5 pieces of C1 hard evidence (medium blue)

More than 5 pieces of C1 hard evidence (dark blue)

Figure 2.1f. The 26 EEA grid cells covered during the 2025 expedition (indicated by yellow shading).

2.2. Methods & results

The data gathered by this study form part of the official wolf monitoring programme of Lower Saxony and as such are integrated into the official database run by the Hunters Association of Lower Saxony (LJN) (LJN 2026b). The data is published in the official LJN quarterly and annual monitoring reports. Data were quality-checked by expedition processes and by the official wolf monitoring programme in line with SCALP categorisation (see [Schütte & Hammer \(2018\)](#) and [Schütte & Hammer \(2019\)](#) for a description of these).

Over two weeks (i.e. two groups) of surveying, citizen scientists walked approximately 650 km, covering 26 cells of the EEA 10 km x 10 km grid in total, some of them multiple times (Fig. 2.1f, Table 2.2a). The monitoring focused on areas with confirmed wolf occurrences and took place exclusively on designated paths - mainly forest and forestry roads (see cover).

Table 2.2a. Number of grid cells and length of routes surveyed by the 2025 expedition teams during the two expedition weeks. Note that the team split into four or fewer groups each day.

Week	Grid cells (N)	Routes total (km)	Routes day 2* (km)	Routes day 3 (km)	Routes day 4 (km)	Routes day 5 (km)	Routes day 6 (km)
1	21	305.18	4.22	78.07	76.86	70.03	69.05
2	17	344.94	26.85	73.00	74.04	68.89	86.08
Total	26	650.12					

* Day 2: training day, survey in one group

The expedition gathered 79 wolf scats, which were good enough to be admitted for SCALP assessment. Thirteen of the 79 samples were fresh enough (less than 48 hours old) to yield material for DNA analysis, 75 of the 79 scats were suitable for dietary analysis (see Table 2.2b)

Table 2.2b. Samples gathered by the expedition and submitted for analysis in 2025.

Scat samples total	Scat samples for dietary analysis	Scat samples for genetic analysis
79	75	13

In total, 9 (11%) of the 79 samples collected were classified as C1 pieces of hard evidence, 14 (18%) as C2 confirmed observations, 51 (66%) as C3a unconfirmed observations (very likely to originate from wolf), one sample was scored as C3 (1% of the total). Four samples were assigned to another species (fox) and therefore classed as “f” (= false) (Fig. 2.2a).

Figure 2.2a. The 89 scat samples collected by the expedition by their SCALP classification.

In week 1, six samples were classed as C1, seven as C2, one as C3, 30 as C3a and only four as f. In week 2, three samples were scored as C1, seven as C2, 21 as C3a (Fig. 2.2b).

Figure 2.2b. The 79 scat samples collected by the expedition in 2025 by their SCALP classification.

Genetics

Of the 13 genetic samples analysed, nine were confirmed by DNA to be of wolf. One of these samples may possibly be a first genetic detection (scat sampled within the Garlstorf territory on 10 July 2025). Three of the nine samples were from known individuals (see Table 2.2c).

Table 2.2c. Details of known wolf individuals re-detected by the expedition.

Individual ID	Sex	Territory	Comments
GW4285f	female	Göhrde	
GW4805f	female	Garlstorf	Born in 2024
GW3103ff	female	Wendisch Evern	

Food analysis

121 scat samples collected by expeditions in eleven wolf territories throughout Lower Saxony in June and August 2022 (n=38) and 2023 (n=83) were analysed in 2025 for prey species composition using DNA metabarcoding. Results are shown in Fig. 2.2c.

Figure 2.2c. Frequency of occurrence of prey species of all scat samples (other prey includes *Vulpes vulpes*, *Microtus agrestis*, *Gallus gallus*) (Schäfer & Karthun-Strijbos 2025).

Roe deer *Capreolus capreolus* was found in 75% of all samples, red deer *Cervus elaphus* in 35% and wild boar *Sus scrofa* in 13%. Nutria *Myocastor coypus*, European hare *Lepus europaeus*, European rabbit *Oryctolagus cuniculus* and others such as fox *Vulpes vulpes*, short-tailed field vole *Microtus agrestis* and fowl *Gallus gallus* were found in rates below 10%. Livestock (cattle, sheep, fowl) was detected at very low rates below 5%.

No significant differences in diet use between the eleven territories were found. However, minor differences in the range of food items consumed can be observed (see Fig. 2.2d). Livestock played no significant role in any of them.

Figure 2.2d. Weighted frequency of occurrence: percentage of prey species per sampled territory. Territory names are displayed within the circles (Schäfer & Karthun-Strijbos 2025).

Food analysis of the samples collected by the 2025 expedition will be included in the 2026 expedition report.

There is still a significant backlog of analysis due to staff shortages at the University of Veterinary Medicine in Hanover. This includes samples from expeditions in the years 2017 - 2022. As soon as results are known, they will be published in a report.

2.3. Discussion & conclusions

Efficiency of effort – data quantity and quality

The expeditions continue to add a high quantity of data to state wolf monitoring efforts. In 2025 the expedition contributed 12% of all wolf scats reported in Lower Saxony over nine months, despite sampling for only two weeks. The data provided by the expedition was also of high quality, accounting for nine out of ten high-certainty C1 samples recorded in the official monitoring programme during Q3 2025 and up to 66% of all C1 samples since expeditions began in 2017 (see Fig. 2.3a). Ultimately, these results demonstrate that citizen scientists can produce high-quality wildlife data with only 1.5 days of professional training.

Figure 2.3a. Proportions of C1 scats from the expeditions (BE) and from the official monitoring programme (LJN).

Areas of wolf activity

Successful wolf surveys rely on a combination of motivated citizen scientists and strategic coordination with local stakeholders, such as foresters and hunters, to target specific wolf territories effectively. This is why the expedition is so successful despite short survey periods, with most of the scat samples assessed with C1 and C2 (n=23) were found in the wolf territories of Amt Neuhaus (n=5), Góhrde (n=4), Wendisch Evern (n=4) and Schneverdingen (n=3).

Wolf population dynamics

A total of three wolf individuals were identified via DNA samples collected by the expedition in 2025. Seven individuals were identified in 2023, eight in 2022, four in 2020, ten in 2019, also ten in 2018 and six in 2017 (Table 2.3a). No wolf individuals were detected twice in 2025. However, multiple wolf scats that could not be assigned to a specific individual were found, so it cannot be ruled out that scats from the same wolf were collected multiple times.

Table 2.3a. Number of wolves identified by DNA samples of the expedition years.

2017	2018	2019	2020	2022	2023	2025
6	10	10	4	8	6	3

NB: No expeditions in 2021 (due to COVID) and 2024 (due to staff sabbatical).

The official monitoring programme currently lacks sufficient DNA samples to provide a complete picture of wolf territory borders, kinship and migration routes. While reproduction was detected in 92% of German wolf packs in 2024/25, the future population size remains uncertain as [Germany has just legalised counterproductive wolf hunting laws](#). In high-density areas, packs are increasingly exhibiting "double reproduction," where multiple females within one pack bear offspring to better defend their territory. Active monitoring is becoming both more difficult and more vital as these pack compositions shift and the impacts of possible wolf hunting must be tracked. Consequently, citizen science projects like Biosphere Expeditions are essential for generating the high-quality data needed to understand how the wolf population and its territories are evolving.

No direct wolf encounter/sighting was registered by the expedition in 2025 (see Table 2.3b for all years). From this it is clear that wolf encounters are exceedingly rare in the wild. Also, while rising wolf populations naturally lead to more frequent sightings in human-dominated landscapes, these encounters do not indicate that the species is losing its inherent fear of humans or becoming "tame". Instead, wolves simply treat infrastructure like roads and buildings as normal parts of their habitat, and claims that they are becoming dangerously conspicuous are largely exaggerated.

Table 2.3b. Number of wolf sightings by the expedition over the years.

Year	2017	2018	2019	2020	2022	2023	2025
Number of sight encounters	0	1	2	0	1	1	0
Survey km	1,100	750	743	246	837	791	650

NB: No expeditions in 2021 (due to COVID) and 2024 (due to staff sabbatical).

Genetics

The Göhrde female GW4285f detected by the expedition was born between 2021 and 2023, and is an offspring of the original Göhrde wolf pack. Her parents are male wolf GW1559m and "old" female wolf GW432f. GW4285f mated with the resident male (her biological father) for the first time in 2024. In 2025, there seemed to be two sets of parents in the Göhrde: male wolf GW1559m, together with one of his daughters, namely GW2975f in the eastern part and another, new male wolf with daughter GW4285f in the western part of the Göhrde forest. The "old female" wolf of the Göhrde pack who was approximately 12 years old, could not be detected in the territory since June 2025 and is presumably dead. Detection of GW4285f by the expedition in 2025 helps to get elucidate territories within the Göhrde forest.

The phenomenon, in which a male wolf of one pack mates with two different females at one time / within a year, is called "double reproduction". It has only been observed for a few years and so far only in some territories. It is assumed that this phenomenon is linked to increasing wolf density. In areas with high wolf density, having a larger pack size compared to neighbouring packs can be an advantage (Ilka Reinhardt, pers. Comm.).

Wolf feeding ecology

A wide variety of studies, including this one, have now shown that wolves in Germany prey predominantly on wild ungulates and that livestock are only rarely part of their diet. These fact-based scientific studies debunk exaggerated reports by some politicians and sections of the media of wolves killing livestock on a significant scale.

Analysis of wolf scats collected during the 2017, 2022 and 2023 expeditions indicates that wild ungulates, specifically roe deer, red deer, and wild boar, constitute the primary food base for wolves in Lower Saxony, with no or very few livestock remains found in all samples. These findings corroborate broader research suggesting that livestock consumption is generally rare when compared to wild prey (DBBW 2018), though this can vary based on regional prey availability and the effectiveness of livestock protection. While metabarcoding results align with previous studies identifying these three ungulates as the main prey species in Germany (Holzapfel et al. 2019, observed fluctuations – such as a higher frequency of red deer over wild boar – are likely due to seasonal availability, as wild boar are more vulnerable in autumn and winter, whereas red deer calves are born in summer. Furthermore, wolf diet is influenced by environmental factors like nut production and winter severity, as well as the specific hunting preferences of individual pack members (Holzapfel et al. 2019). Ultimately, while scat analysis provides a vital overview of the food spectrum, continuous and seasonal sampling remains essential to fully capture the impact of prey shifts and potential livestock predation.

Local stakeholder and cooperations

Despite initial opposition in 2017 from authorities and anti-wolf lobbyists, cooperation has improved significantly, with the State Forestry Department now specifically requesting surveys in certain areas. This shift allowed the expedition to successfully gather indirect wolf signs and identify new individuals by using established survey routes (Schütte and Hammer 2019). Strategic collaboration with local wolf commissioners, foresters, and hunters enabled more targeted searches, explaining why recent findings have increased since the inaugural 2017 expedition (Schütte and Hammer 2018). The expedition values this newfound trust, which has transformed their ability to contribute high-quality data to the official monitoring database.

Summary and Outlook

[Germany has just officially integrated the wolf into national hunting law](#), a move following the EU's decision to downgrade the species' status from "strictly protected" to "protected." Critics such as NABU and WWF argue this shift is politically motivated rather than science-based, as the wolf's conservation status is not yet "favourable." While proponents claim hunting will balance livestock protection and public safety, research suggests that culling does not effectively reduce livestock kills; instead, success depends on localised livestock protection measures. Furthermore, illegal killings remain a significant threat, accounting for 9% of documented wolf deaths, including disturbing cases of poaching and decapitation.

Despite this shift towards lawful hunting, the Biosphere Expeditions continues to demonstrate that well-trained citizen scientists provide the precise, objective data necessary to counter misinformation and emotional polarisation. By collaborating with once-skeptical

forestry officials and local stakeholders, the project has proven that active monitoring can foster coexistence and identify economic opportunities in wolf-based tourism. In an era where "problem wolves" can now be legally targeted, factual data on pack composition and territory borders is more essential than ever to ensure management decisions remain grounded in reality rather than populist rhetoric.

Livestock owners facing real risks should receive unbureaucratic, nationwide support and compensation rather than promoting wolf shooting as a primary solution, as studies indicate that regulated hunting has no long-term effect on reducing attacks (Reinhardt et al. 2012, Bruns et al. 2020). Instead, an effective management strategy requires regionally active, trained professionals who work closely with local stakeholders to provide direct, low-threshold assistance and science-based expertise on the ground.

Illegal killings remain the second most common cause of wolf mortality in Germany, with 9% of the 1,286 wolves found dead between 2000 and 2025 being victims of crime (DBBW 2024). In the 2024/25 monitoring year alone, 10% of examined carcasses were illegally shot, while others showed signs of surviving previous gunshot wounds. High-profile cases, such as the poaching of wolf GW1039m and the discovery of severed heads in Leiferde, highlight a disturbing trend of wildlife crime that likely involves many more unreported cases. Consequently, there is an urgent need for investigative authorities to strengthen the prosecution and punishment of these offences to effectively protect the population.

Beyond the challenges of wolf presence¹, there are significant ecological and economic opportunities, such as rural communities generating income through specialised nature tourism, the expedition has been a showcase for this for many years. Furthermore, wolves provide a natural service by regulating herbivore browsing, which directly supports forest regeneration (CHWOLF 2020).

Now in its eighth year, this project has exceeded all expectations by demonstrating that well-trained citizen scientists can acquire highly valuable data through targeted monitoring. These productive results have successfully refuted initial doubts from hunters, forestry officials and landowners, leading to a significant shift in attitudes toward the utility of citizen science in wolf conservation.

Recommendations for future expeditions

To ensure continued success, future expeditions should be conducted annually, with methods and logistics refined through regular reviews. Broader support from wolf commissioners and nature conservation authorities, alongside improved communication with stakeholders like hunting associations and forestry departments, is helpful and should be pursued. By offering collaborative opportunities such as camera trapping and sign surveys, the project can further integrate local, national, and international citizen scientists. Additionally, seeking grants to fund free placements and working with the media will encourage greater local participation and strengthen the project's impact.

¹ Recently brought into sharp focus by a [stressed juvenile wolf attacking, apparently in self-defence, a member of the public in a highly urbanised area of downtown Hamburg](#). It is the first recorded wolf attack on a human since wolves returned to Germany nearly 30 years ago, with the disorientated juvenile likely wandering into the city by accident.

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Appendix I: Week-by-week survey results

Effort & results week 1

Survey days		5/6*
EEA 10x10 km grid cells covered		21
Scats collected**		30
Day	Distance covered by teams (km)	Remarks
Sat, 05. July	5.60	Pre-expedition
Sun, 06 July	4.22	One training group only
Mon, 07 July	78.07	
Tue, 08 July	76.86	
Wed, 9 July	70.03	
Thu, 10 July	69.50	
Total	304.28	

*pre-expedition included; **C1, C2, C3 and C3a

Figure Ia. 21 EEA grid cells covered during week 1 of the 2025 expedition (indicated as yellow shading).

Effort & results week 2

Survey days	5/7*
EEA 10x10 km grid cells covered	17
Scats collected**	21

Day	Distance covered by teams (km)	Remarks
Fri, 11 July	17.77	Pre-expedition
Sat, 12 July	15.00	Pre-expedition
Sun, 13 July	26.85	One training group only
Mon, 14 July	73.00	
Tue, 15 July	74.40	
Wed, 16 July	68.89	
Thu, 17 July	86.80	
Total	362.71	

*pre-expedition included; **C1, C2, C3 and C3a

Figure IId. 21 EEA grid cells covered during week 2 of the 2025 expedition (indicated as yellow shading).